

To Identify Specific Age Group and Distribution of Carcinoma Breast in Females

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background & Methods: The aim of the study is to identify specific age group and distribution of carcinoma breast in females. All biopsy / FNAC proven cases of Ca breast in females.

Results: In our study we found maximum no. of cases in age group of 41-50 i.e. 29.5%, followed by 25.5% in age group of 31-40. Maximum cases in stage II (45%) followed by 38% in stage III. We found Postmenopausal (67%), Perimenopausal (18%) & Menstruating (15%)

Conclusion: Carcinoma of Breast is the most commonly site-specific cancer in women & is the leading cause of death from cancer for female 35-50 years of age. Breast Cancer accounts for 32% of all female cancer and is responsible for 19% of the cancer related deaths in women. In our study most common presenting complaint is lump in breast (98%). In our study most common presenting complaint is lump in breast (98%).

Keywords: age, carcinoma, breast & females.

Study Design: Observational Study

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Introduction

In India, breast cancer incidence peaks among women 45–50 years of age. The average age of patients in six hospital-based cancer registries ranged from 44.2 in Dibrugarh, 46.8 in Delhi, 47 in Jaipur to 49.6 in Bangalore and Chennai. Among patients at SGPGIMS in Lucknow, 26% were younger than 35 years of age, whereas at TMH, Mumbai, this percentage was 11% [1].

In general prognosis of carcinoma breast seems to be based on dynamic interplay between the anatomic extent of cancer when it is first diagnosed and its growth potential i.e. aggressiveness or virulence on one side versus the degree of immunocompetence of the host and appropriate early treatment on the other side [2&3].

Cancer staging is representative of the anatomical extent or advancement of cancer when diagnosed. The vast majority of patients with breast cancer show a direct relationship between the stage of the cancer when diagnosed and the length of survival [4]. There are many systems of breast cancer staging based on clinical, surgical, pathologic and autopsy

evaluation. The one that is in universal use is the TNM system. It offers details regarding T (tumor size), N (node status) and M (metastasis) for the general purpose of prognosis. Before deciding on definitive treatment for a newly diagnosed breast cancer, staging the disease is necessary to plan optimum treatment. Lymph node involvement makes a full auxiliary clearance more appropriate, whereas distant spread of disease may indicate primary chemotherapy [5].

Material and Methods

Present study was conducted at Sri Aurobindo Medical College and PG institute, Indore (M.P.) for 01 Year. All biopsy / FNAC proven cases of Ca breast in females on 200.

No exclusion or inclusion criteria will be followed. All patients with breast cancer recorded.

Result

Table 1: Age group distribution of Carcinoma Breast patients

S. No.	Age Group (Years)	No. of Cases	Percentage
1.	< 20	02	01
2.	20-30	05	2.5
3.	31-40	51	25.5
4.	41-50	59	29.5
5.	51-60	42	21
6.	61-70	20	10
7.	>70	21	10.5

In our study we found maximum no. of cases in age group of 41-50 i.e. 29.5%, followed by 25.5% in age group of 31-40.

Table 2: Stagewise distribution of patients

S.No.	Stage	Percent of Patients (%)
1.	0	00
2.	I	01
3.	II	45
4.	III	38
5.	IV	16

Maximum cases in stage II (45%) followed by 38% in stage III.

Table 3: Menstrual status wise distribution of patients

S. No.	MENSTRUAL STATUS	Percentage of cases
1.	Menstruating	15
2.	Perimenopausal	18
3.	Postmenopausal	67

We found Postmenopausal (67%), Perimenopausal (18%) & Menstruating (15%)

Table 4: Complaint-wise distribution of patients

S. No.	Complain	Percentage of cases
1.	Breast Lump	98
2.	Mastalgia	58.2
3.	Nipple discharge	10.25
4.	Breast skin involvement	02

Discussion

In our study mean age at presentation is 40 years, and age distribution of other related studies has been taken for comparison. As compare to previous literature studies, the mean age at diagnosis of our study is found to be 40 years which is 10 years less to National Cancer Registry for 1984, 20 years less as compared to Oxford study. This difference is due to Tripple Assessment [6].

Based on the figures of the National Cancer Registry for 1984, the mean age at diagnosis of breast cancer is 50.05 years. This figure is 10 years less than the mean age at diagnosis at Oxford (U.K.) for which the figure is 60.82 years [7]. In our study the main bulk of cases (approximately 76%) are in age group 40-59 years. In our study the main bulk of cases (approximately 54%) are in age group 35-55 years,

which indicates shifting of age group towards early age.

Women whose menarche occurs before the age of 12 years have a relative risk of 2.30 compared to those starting menstruation after this age. This decreases as the age of onset of menstruation increases. The reduction in the age of the menarche over the past 100 years, especially in the western world, probably results from improved nutrition and general health and may be important in the demographic variations in incidence of breast cancer [8].

The risk of developing breast cancer also related to the age of the menopause. The relative risk of developing breast cancer is 0.5% in those who cease to menstruate before the age of 45, compared to women who continue menstruating beyond age 55. Artificial menopause by Oophorectomy or irradiation also reduces the risk of breast cancer.

In our study premenopausal patients were 15%, perimenopausal patients were 18% and postmenopausal patients were 67%. This data is much different to what was obtained by Meanser (1964) 72.2%; Wolfe (1965) 82% and Trehow (1970) 75.75% [9]. This indicates most patients of carcinoma breast belong to postmenopausal group.

Conclusion

Carcinoma of Breast is the most commonly site-specific cancer in women & is the leading cause of death from cancer for female 35-50 years of age. Breast Cancer accounts for 32% of all female cancer and is responsible for 19% of the cancer related deaths in women. In our study most common presenting complaint is lump in breast (98%). In our study most common presenting complaint is lump in breast (98%).

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